

IMPACT OF INTEGRATED CURRICULUM APPROACH ON STUDENT ACHIEVEMENT

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Abstract

The changing nature of knowledge in recent times is argued to be a key reason why educators need to consider curriculum integration. Curriculum integration is a curriculum design that repositions subject content through collaboration and experience in order to increase its meaning and relevance to students, holding less regard for disciplinary boundaries than traditional didactical approaches. The purpose of this research is to study the effectiveness of Integrated Curriculum Approach (ICA) in the learning of science among the secondary school students. In order to test the effectiveness of the approach across the different boards namely SSC, CBSE and CIE the researcher adopted an experimental study. The sample for the study consisted of 260 students of English medium Secondary Schools affiliated to SSC, CBSE and CIE board from Mumbai and Navi Mumbai. A multivariate analysis ANOVA employed to evaluate results of the study. The significance of the approach with the integrated system were tested using t test.

Keywords: *Integrated curriculum approach (ICA), Traditional Approach (TA), Academic achievement, Secondary, School, Students*

Introduction:

The functions of education and learning have undergone profound transformation because of the drastic changes in the globe. To prepare students for the difficulties and opportunities of the modern world, education in the twenty-first century must encourage 21st century abilities like critical thinking, communication, teamwork, and creativity in addition to teaching

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conventional skills. Throughout a student's life, 21st century learning abilities can be applied to all academic and multidisciplinary fields as well as civic situations. The term "21st Century Learning" is used to describe a form of education that does not rely on traditional teaching methods or rote memorization but rather involves developing students' real-world skills to meet the demands and challenges of a constantly changing global economy.

Twenty-first-century learning embodies an approach to teaching that links content to skill. Its paradigm offers an opportunity to synergize the margins of the content with core concepts and makes learning more meaningful. Embracing a 21st-century learning model requires consideration of those elements that could comprise such a shift: creating learners who take intellectual risks, fostering learning dispositions, and nurturing school communities where everyone is a learner.

Thus integrating core concepts with key skills will prepare students for the workplace and college. We need to go beyond mile-wide and inch-deep coverage of ever expanding information in the classroom in order to achieve this. As a result, the teacher plays a crucial role in helping pupils in the classroom to acquire the necessary abilities. As rightly stated by Albert Einstein., "We cannot solve our problem with the same thinking we used when we created them". Therefore, it is imperative to have a new outlook towards curriculum planning and thus acclimatize new strategies of teaching methodologies into teaching and learning.

Interdisciplinary methods have been used in secondary schools in New Zealand as far back as the 1940s, while the 1970s and 1980s saw a spike in popularity for thematic methods in elementary schools worldwide. Paul Hirst and Basil Bernstein, two well-known and important English educators, argued on curricular integration in the 1970s. Bernstein advocated an integrated strategy that required "the subordination of previously insulated disciplines or courses to some relational idea". It was believed that connecting subjects using a relational idea may make studying more interesting for pupils and give them learning opportunities in real-world situations. Different subjects might offer different interpretations of a particular topic or problem. More recently, the idea of curriculum integration has re-emerged as one of the key themes of twenty-first century learning. In this context, curriculum integration is most often linked with inquiry learning.

What is Curriculum Integration?

Curriculum integration is like white light – a combination of all the different colors of the learning spectrum. These colors are useful and have their place individually, mix a couple together to make new understanding and all together in equal parts to produce the overall white light. White light is what you use to see clearly, an uneven mix will just eventually hurt your eyes.
(Misty, Rua High)

The meaning of curriculum integration varies from source to source, and schools and teachers integrate curriculum in different ways. James Beane, a prominent advocate for curriculum integration (1993, 1997, 2005), understands curriculum integration to involve meaningful learning organized around issues important to teachers and students; in this way, curriculum integration supports democracy (Beane, 2005). Beane outlined four aspects of integration that emphasize issues and align with democratic principles: integration of experiences, social integration, integration of knowledge, and integration as a curriculum design. Integration of experiences means that past and present experiences are integrated to facilitate new learning. Social integration occurs when students from diverse cultural perspectives enjoy common learning experiences. Integration of knowledge happens when content area concepts are integrated through a focus on issues. Integration as a design emphasizes project-based learning and other applications of knowledge (Beane, 1993). Beane (1997) anchored his concept of curriculum integration in his principles for middle schools, namely that curriculum should be general, and helpful for young adolescents exploring self and social meanings.

Curriculum integration “engages students as active learners who make the most of the decisions about what they study” (Brown, 2016, p. 123). Designed to be responsive to students’ concerns, curriculum integration allows for a model in which “students become teachers and teachers become learners” (Pate, 2013, p. 174). Springer (2006), a leading practitioner, further noted that “curriculum integration takes as its ultimate aim helping students live better lives now as well as in the future, not merely gathering more information for possible later use” (p.14). Similarly, Dowden (2007), writing about curriculum integration in Australian middle schools, stated that its main purpose is to “resituate subject matter into relevant and meaningful contexts” (p.52). Topics, themes, and issues that are meaningful for

students can provide a starting point for curriculum integration (Jacobs, 1989; Nesin & Lounsbury, 1999).

Researchers, administrators, teachers, and teacher educators have interpreted curriculum integration in various ways. They also have used different terminology to describe their approaches because, as researchers and practitioners have noted, there is little consensus on what terms like curriculum integration, interdisciplinary curriculum, content integration, core curriculum, and multidisciplinary curriculum.

Rationale for Integration

As educators, we are constantly searching for new ways to help students make sense of the multitude of life's experiences and the bits and pieces of knowledge they gain from a traditionally departmentalized curriculum. Students today continue to move from one discipline to the next forcing the information to be disconnected to anything that resembles real life situations. To lighten some of the fragmentation our students and teachers experience, holistic and integrated curriculums are being proposed and adopted by many school districts. A major driving force behind integrated teaching and learning is the belief that when themes, subjects, or projects are combined students begin to see meaningful connections between the subject matter. Material then serves as a vehicle for learning rather than simply pieces of information.

For example, the connections between science and mathematics were made more apparent by scientific developments that took into account the orientations of value and the digitisation theories of mathematics. Mathematics and science integration is justified for several reasons (Ibrahim, 2002; Lee et al., 2011; Merrill & Comerford, 2004; Obaid, 2004). First, mathematics can be characterised by a high degree of abstraction; thus, the integration of science with mathematics represents an opportunity to provide real-life examples of mathematical principles. Second, mathematical concepts can be effectively used during science teaching in order to make scientific concepts more meaningful. Third, both mathematics and science rely on concepts, axioms, functions, theories, and practice; thus, there is a significant degree of structural consistency that allows for integration. Fourth, life situations tend to be characterised by a high degree of flexibility, which means that it is possible to integrate the concepts of science and mathematics in a logical sequence. Finally, there is a strong link

between mathematical and scientific reasoning and other types of thinking, particularly creative, critical, and deductive thinking (Ibrahim, 2002; Lee et al., 2011; Merrill & Comerford, 2004; Obaid, 2004).

Research Design

The concept of Integrated curriculum evolved right from the John Dewey period, where the major proponents believed in Progressive education. These clearly depicted the fact that knowledge cannot be bound within the disciplines. This turned the aspect to a shift in approach, which widely concentrated across teaching, learning and assessment. An emphasis laid with an objective to teach to develop mental, physical and moral growth of the whole person. The knowledge base of the scientific approach linked with the problem solving approach with a realm to link the knowledge with the real world problems. However looking at the present scenario, there is still a decline in the level of achievement attained by the learners. The research studies implicated varied reason for the decline. The reasons ranged from their socio economic background to the level of pedagogy attained in school. Thus, the researcher ought to study the interaction effect of the Integrated curriculum approach to curriculum transaction with reference to the type school (SSC, CBSE, CIE) among secondary school students.

The researcher formulated a research design in order to implement the approach and test its effectiveness. The probable research design incorporated four major areas – Disciplinary grounding, Synthesizing, Communicating and Reflecting. These dimensions catered with reference to both alternative to teaching and learning.

Research Question: To what extent is the Integrated Curriculum Approach (ICA) to curriculum transaction is effective at the secondary school students?

Hypothesis: There is no significant main effect as well as the interaction effects of the Integrated Curriculum Approach of curriculum transaction and the type of schools (SSC,

CBSE, and CIE) on the achievement among secondary school students.

Variables of the study:

Independent Variable: Integrated Curriculum Approach

Dependent Variable: Achievement

Statistical analysis

I. Descriptive Data Analysis

a) Descriptive statistics of TAS and ICAS of the Total Sample

The following table 1.1 shows the descriptive statistics of TAS and ICAS of the total sample

TOTAL SAMPLE		
Descriptive statistics	TAS	ICAS
N	130	130
Mean	29.62	39.60
Standard Error	0.46	0.40
Median	30.00	40.00
Mode	30.00	40.00
Standard Deviation	5.27	4.57
Sample Variance	27.82	20.86
Kurtosis	-0.85	1.30
Skewness	-0.42	-1.13
Skewness	-0.42	-1.13

Table 1.1: Descriptive statistics of TAS and ICAS of the Total Sample

Interpretation: The mean, median and mode of TAS and ICAS from the above data differed by some factor. The standard deviation, skewness and and kurtosis values indicated that the data is normally distributed.

Fiduciary limits of mean and standard deviation of TAS and ICAS of the Total Sample

The following table 1.2 shows the fiduciary limits of mean and standard deviation of TAS and ICAS of the total sample.

TOTAL SAMPLE		
Descriptive statistics	TAS	ICAS
Mean	29.62	39.60
Standard Error	0.46	0.40
Fiduciary limits at 0.95 level	28.71 : 30.54	38.81 : 40.39
Fiduciary limits at 0.99 level	28.41 : 30.83	38.55 : 40.65

Table 1.2: Fiduciary limits of mean and standard deviation of TAS and ICAS of the Total

Sample

From the above table we could infer that,

- Of 100 of the total sample, 95 times the population mean of the TAS will be between 28.71 and 30.54 while 99 times the population mean of the TAS will be between 28.41 and 30.83.
- Of 100 of the total sample, 95 times the population mean of the ICAS will be between 38.81 and 40.39 while 99 times the population mean of the ICAS will be between 38.55 and 40.65.

Percent mean of TAS and ICAS of the Total Sample

The following table 1.3 shows the percent mean of TAS and ICAS of the total sample.

	TA	ICA
N	130	130
Percent Mean	22.79	30.46

Table 1.3: The percent mean of TAS and ICAS of the Total Sample

Figure 1.1: Graphical representation of the percent mean of TAS and ICAS of the Total Sample

I. Descriptive analysis of TAS and ICAS based on Type of School

The following table 1.4 shows the descriptive statistics of TAS and ICAS based on Type of School.

<i>Descriptive statistics</i>	TAS			ICAS		
	SSC	CBSE	CIE	SSC	CBSE	CIE
Mean	29.56	29.47	29.88	39.31	39.60	39.93
Standard Error	0.77	0.84	0.81	0.63	0.71	0.76
Median	31.00	31.00	30.00	41.00	40.00	41.00
Mode	30.00	35.00	30.00	41.00	40.00	40.00
Standard Deviation	5.17	5.64	5.09	4.19	4.78	4.81
Sample Variance	26.71	31.75	25.96	17.58	22.88	23.15
Kurtosis	-1.01	-1.27	0.12	0.08	0.47	0.21
Skewness	-0.38	-0.31	-0.65	-0.84	-1.60	-0.93

Table 1.4: Descriptive statistics of TAS and ICAS based on Type of School

Interpretation: The mean, median and mode of TAS and ICAS from the above data differed by some factor. The standard deviation, skewness and and kurtosis values indicated that the data is normally distributed.

Fiduciary limits of mean and standard deviation of TAS and ICAS based on Type of School

The following table 1.5 shows the fiduciary limits of mean and standard deviation of TAS and ICAS based on Type of School.

<i>Descriptive statistics</i>	TAS			ICAS		
	SSC	CBSE	CIE	SSC	CBSE	CIE
Mean	29.56	29.47	29.88	39.31	39.60	39.93
Standard Error	0.77	0.84	0.81	0.63	0.71	0.76
Fiduciary limits at 0.95 level	28.00 : 31.11	27.77 : 31.16	28.25: 31.50	38.05 : 40.57	38.16 : 41.04	38.39 : 41.46
Fiduciary limits at 0.99 level	27.48 : 31.63	27.21 : 31.73	27.69 : 32.06	37.63 : 40.99	37.68 : 41.52	37.87 : 41.98

Table 1.5: Fiduciary limits of mean and standard deviation of TAS and ICAS based on Type of School.

From the above table we could infer that,

Of 100 of the total sample of SSC school students,

- 95 times the population mean of the TAS will be between 28.00 and 31.11 while 99 times the population mean of the TAS will be between 27.48 and 31.63.
- 95 times the population mean of the ICAS will be between 38.05 and 40.57 while 99 times the population mean of the ICAS will be between 37.63 and 40.99.

Of 100 of the total sample of CBSE school students,

- 95 times the population mean of the TAS will be between 27.77 and 31.16 while 99 times the population mean of the TAS will be between 27.21 and 31.73.
- 95 times the population mean of the ICAS will be between 38.16 and 41.04 while 99 times the population mean of the ICAS will be between 37.68 and 41.52.

Of 100 of the total sample of CIE school students,

- 95 times the population mean of the TAS will be between 28.25 and 31.50 while 99 times the population mean of the TAS will be between 27.69 and 32.06.
- 95 times the population mean of the ICAS will be between 38.39 and 41.46 while 99 times the population mean of the ICAS will be between 37.87 and 41.52.

Percent mean of TAS and ICAS based on Type of School

The following table 1.6 shows the percent mean of TAS and ICAS based on Type of School.

	TAS			ICAS		
	SSC	CBSE	CIE	SSC	CBSE	CIE
N	45	45	40	45	45	40
Percent Mean	59.11	58.93	59.75	78.62	79.20	79.85

Table 1.6: The percent mean of TAS and ICAS based on Type of School

Figure 1.2: Graphical representation of the percent mean of TAS and ICAS based on Type of School.

I. Verification of the H_0 :

There is no significant main effect as well as the interaction effects of the Integrated Curriculum Approach of curriculum transaction and the type of schools (SSC, CBSE, and CIE) on the achievement among secondary school students.

The statistical technique used to test this hypothesis was two way ANOVA.

The following table 5.3 shows the inferential statistics of TA and ICA in reference to the Type of School.

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F_{crit}</i>	<i>LOS</i>
SS between approaches	6750	1	6750	277.10	4.94E-43	3.84	S at 0.01
SS between the type of school	28.47	2	14.23	0.58	0.56	3.00	NS
Interaction	2.02	2	1.01	0.04	0.96	3.00	NS
Error	6430.98	26	24.34				
Total	13211.47	26					

Table 5.3: Main effect and Interaction effects of the TA and ICA in reference to the type of school.

Interpretation of data:

1. The calculated $F= 277.10$ (SS between the approaches) is significant at 0.01 level and therefore, the null hypothesis regarding the main effect of approaches and the type of school is rejected at 0.01 level. As a result, it is possible to draw the conclusion that the methods to curriculum transaction (ICA, TA) have a considerable primary influence on the achievement of type of school among secondary school students.
2. The calculated $F=0.58$ (SS between type of school) is not significant at 0.01 level and therefore, the null hypothesis regarding the main effect of approaches on the level of achievement is accepted at 0.01 level. As a result, it is possible to draw the conclusion that the methods to curriculum transaction (ICA, TA) does not have a considerable primary influence within the type of school (SSC, CBSE and CIE) among secondary school students.

3. The calculated $F=0.04$ (Interaction) is not significant at 0.01 level and therefore, the null hypothesis regarding the interaction effect of approaches and the type of school on the achievement is accepted at 0.01 level. As a result, it is possible to draw the conclusion that the methods to curriculum transaction (ICA, TA) and the type of school does not have a considerable interaction effect on the achievement among secondary school students.

Conclusion:

1. There is significant main effect of the Integrated Curriculum Approach mode to curriculum transaction and the type of school on the achievement among the secondary school students.
2. There is no significant main effect of the Integrated Curriculum Approach mode to curriculum transaction within the type of school (SSC, CBSE and CIE).
3. There is no significant interaction effect of the Integrated Curriculum Approach mode to curriculum transaction and the type of school (SSC, CBSE and CIE) on achievement of the students.

Discussion:

The activity method encourages inquiry, offers chances for modelling and identification, involves students in engaging experiences and practical tasks, and sparks activities involving problem-solving. When utilising a strategy that depends on a question-centered integrating agent, the limits experienced by teachers were less severe and simpler to work with.

There are several advantages to an integrated curriculum. Students benefit from integrated education because it fosters a love of learning, boosts self-confidence, develops a commitment to the democratic group process, and sharpens students' critical thinking and empathy abilities (Vars, 2001). Students' impressions of their language arts and social studies integrated curriculum experiences were solicited by Erlandson and McVittie (2001). The ability to relate academic subject to practical experiences was noted by students. They started connecting the information they learned in class with their real lives as their style of thinking changed. The pupils also understood how the curriculum's integration brought each discipline together into a single entity.³

Further a t-test was conducted to ascertain the significance among the type of school namely SSC, CBSE and CIE.

The following table 5.4 shows the inferential statistics for signifying the difference between TA and ICA in reference to the type of school.

	Mean	Variance	df	tstat	P(T<=t) 2-tail	tcrit 2-tail	LOS
SSC & CBSE	39.31	17.58	87.00	-0.30	0.76	1.99	NS
	39.60	22.88					
CBSE & CIE	39.60	22.88	88.00	-0.62	0.54	1.99	NS
	40.22	22.36					
SSC & CIE	39.31	17.58	87.00	-0.97	0.34	1.99	NS
	40.22	22.36					

Table 5.4: Inferential statistics for signifying the difference between TA and ICA in reference to the type of school.

Interpretation of data:

1. The calculated $t = -0.30$ is less than t critical = 1.99 among SSC and CBSE type of school. Thus 't' is not significant at 0.01 level.
2. The calculated $t = -0.62$ is less than t critical = 1.99 among CBSE and CIE type of school. Thus 't' is not significant at 0.01 level.
3. The calculated $t = -0.97$ is less than t critical = 1.99 among SSC and CIE type of school. Thus 't' is not significant at 0.01 level.

Conclusion:

This concludes that impact of integrated curriculum approach to curriculum transaction has uniformly benefited all the type of schools.

Discussion:

The type of schools (SSC, CBSE and CIE) have different approaches to curriculum planning. Irrespective of the fact, each one of them promotes usage of effective teaching methods in order to achieve the objectives effectively. The method of creating a mind map and building linkages among the different area of study have made the learning more concrete. The integrated activities booted the interest of the students in the different areas of knowledge and thus provided varied opportunities for the real life connections.

Conclusion

The purpose of the present study was to study the effectiveness of integrated curriculum approach on achievement and critical thinking of students. The statistical study proved the

basis for the significance of the approach. Thus, it is evident that the integration of the curriculum is a crucial topic in the realm of education. Curriculum integration has been endorsed as a significant educational intervention by a number of themes that have been found in the research. Despite the fact that majority of the research were broadly looking at the aspects of implementation and thus it was only limited to the viewpoints and the attitudes of the educators. The key arguments in favour of curricular integration in the literature include relevance, readiness for the 21st century, its transformational potential, social skills, connections, and cooperation, problem solving and critical thinking, engagement, accomplishment, and time allocation.

Overall, there is substantial evidence that teaching using an integrated curriculum improves student learning, increases student engagement, and fosters a more positive attitude toward subject.

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